

Stable and Bright Single Active Layer Electrophosphorescent White Polymer Light-Emitting Devices

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Abstract

A white light polymer light emitting devices (PLEDs) was demonstrated with a single layer configuration of the PVK, PBD, FIrpic and Ir(Btp)₂(acac) polymer blend solution. The configuration of the device was ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PVK:PBD:FIrpic:Ir(Btp)₂(acac)/Ca/Al. By adjusting the blended layers, white light emission with the pure white-light emission with CIE coordinates of (0.34, 0.37) is achieved, and changing slightly in a large voltage range, the maximal luminance efficiency 1.8 cd/A is reached at 0.26mA, and the maximal brightness is 3100 cd/m² at 14V.

Introduction

White Polymer light emitting devices (WPLED) have drawn intense attention in both scientific and industrial communities due to their potential applications in full-color flat panel displays, back-lighting sources for liquid-crystal displays and solid-state lighting sources [1]. To achieve white emission, mixtures of the three red, green and blue (RGB) primary colors or two complementary colors, are typically required. Various approaches towards realizing WPLEDs have been reported, including multilayer structures capable of sequential energy transfer, multiple component emissive layers containing an appropriate of RG phosphorescent or fluorescent dopants. Polymer blends containing RGB emitting species, charge transfer exciplexes or excimers broad emission and single component layers that utilize a polymer with broad emission. In this study, we report single layer white PLEDs with an emission layer containing a blend of two phosphorescent iridium complexes within a PVK-PBD host matrix [2-3]. Despite their simple architectures and straightforward fabrication procedures, these devices show excellent color purity and considerably improved luminance efficiencies, when compared to other polymer-based white emission devices.

Experimental

White Polymer light emitting devices were fabricated on the ITO-coated glass substrates. The substrates were ultrasonically cleaned with detergent, deionized water, acetone, and isopropyl alcohol. A layer of 40 nm thick poly(3,4-ethylene dioxythiophene):poly(styrene sulfonic acid) (PEDOT:PSS, H.C. Stack) was spin coated onto the precleaned and UV-O₃ treated ITO substrates. The PEDOT:PSS layer was first baked at 150°C for 30 min to remove residual water and then moved into a glovebox under the N₂ environment to performance the subsequent multilayer integration process. PVK and PBD were obtained from sigma-Aldrich and used as received. FIrpic and Ir(Btp)₂(acac) were purchased from Luminescence technology corp. The blends of PVK:PBD(60:40) with different FIrpic and Ir(Btp)₂(acac) concentrations in dichlorobenzene solution were spin coated on top of

ITO/PEDOT:PSS. The blend layers were about 70 nm thickness. To remove residual solvent, the samples were annealed at 60°C before cathode deposition. Then, the Ca(60nm) and Al(120nm) electrodes were thermally evaporation in a vacuum of about 2×10^{-6} Torr.

Fig. 1 (a) Normalized EL spectra of PLED (b) The luminescence versus voltage characteristics of PLEDs with different FIrpic(blue) Ir(Btp)₂(acac)(red) doping levels; Device structure is ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PVK0.6:PBD0.4: FIrpic(blue): Ir(Btp)₂(acac)(red)/Ca/Al

Results and Discussion

The EL spectra of the device with different weight ratio's are shown in Fig.1 (a). As seen from this figure two main emission peaks appeared and the red peak was slightly blue shifted at 8V. But the white PLED showed good stability. For the device with the different Ir complexes weight ratios of the white emission color is stable. For the luminance varying from 300 cd/m² (which is necessary for display applications) to 3100 cd/m², the CIE coordinates slightly shift from (0.34, 0.37) to (0.36, 0.39). This probably because the exciton recombination zone shifts slightly under an electric field. Luminance –voltage characteristics of devices shown in Fig.1 (b). The turn-on voltage(defined as the voltage where 1 cd/m² is measured) about 8.0V is low among PVK based with white PLEDs, where usually high drive voltages are required. The devices exhibit a maximum brightness of 3100 cd/m² and a maximum luminous efficiency of 1.8 cd/A. The low operation voltages of the devices are important for reducing powder consumption.

References

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